

STUDIES IN GLASS SYSTEM. MAGNETIC SUSCEPTIBILITY OF GOLD DISPERSED IN BORAX-GLASS

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The diamagnetic susceptibility of gold, dispersed in borax glass, has been measured at different concentrations by the magnetic torsion balance. It has been found that the susceptibility of dissolved gold, as calculated from the additivity formula, is greater than the value for pure gold, although the increase is not so high as in the case of alkali sulphates and chlorides, dispersed in the same glass. The reason for this increase has been discussed.

Several papers on the properties of polar crystals and noble metals, dissolved in boric oxide and borax glasses, have been published by Majumdar and co-workers. The magnetic properties of such systems have been recorded in three communications (Majumdar and Saha, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1945, 22, 147; Majumdar and Banerjee, *Indian J. Phys.*, 1946, 18, 217; Majumdar and Majumdar, this issue p. 291; Majumdar, *Nature*, 1948, 161, 685). In these investigations it has been found that alkali chlorides and sulphates show an abnormal increase of diamagnetic susceptibility when dispersed in boric oxide or borax glasses and the increase is quite out of proportion with the value observed in the case of aqueous solutions of these salts. With systems having a salt containing a different cation in borax glass, the observed change may in part be accounted for by cation exchange in the glass. But, noble metals like gold and platinum are not known to form any borates and, hence any change observed in such a system is not due to any compound formation. It is for this reason that gold was selected as the dispersed phase and the magnetic susceptibility of the glass samples was determined. Similar systems with platinum (paramagnetic) have also been studied and will form the subject of a separate communication.

EXPERIMENTAL

Preparation of the samples.—Purified samples of borax (Merck, pro-Analyse quality) were prepared as described in a previous communication (Majumdar and Majumdar, *loc. cit.*). The precaution is necessary as traces of moisture are tenaciously held by glass even if it melted at such a high temperature as 1000° (Turner). An 1% solution of pure gold chloride was prepared in conductivity water and a definite volume was taken in a clean platinum crucible and the solution evaporated on a water-bath. The crucible was then heated on asbestos to about 300° to ensure complete decomposition of gold in a finely divided state. A roughly weighed amount of purified and dehydrated borax was then added and the mixture heated to 800°—1000° until a homogeneous melt was obtained. Above a certain concentration of gold, the excess of the metal separated on the surface and did not enter into the system. The maximum gold content, as found by subsequent analysis, was 3.12%. The crucible was allowed to cool gradually and the solid extracted. The glass was lightly coloured, the shade varying from light grey to pink in transmitted light.

Analysis of the samples.—The percentage of gold in the samples was determined by an electrometric method due to Müller and Weisbrod (*Z. anorg. Chem.*, 1926, 17, 156). To test the accuracy of the method for small concentrations of gold, a standard solution was prepared by dissolving 0.5 g. of pure gold in aqua regia, evaporating the solution on a water-bath and diluting it to 200 c.c. A sudden fall of potential was observed when all the excess of chlorine water was used up:

and the solution contained only trivalent gold. The titration was continued when another sudden drop in potential was observed due to the reduction of trivalent gold to metallic gold:

The amount of FeSO_4 consumed between these two breaks gave the equivalent of Mohr salt corresponding to the gold present. The precipitated gold was sometimes deposited on the electrode, but the results were reproducible in spite of it. Addition of borax lowered the first potential drop by 50 millivolts or so, but the break was quite sharp. The shape of the curve near the first equivalence point was slightly changed. Unfortunately these were not perfectly reproducible. As the equivalence point was calculated from the $(\Delta E/\Delta V, c)$ curves, the actual shape of the curves did not have much effect on the equivalence points found and did not therefore much affect the results.

Determination of the Magnetic Susceptibility of the samples.—The diamagnetic susceptibility of the samples was determined in a magnetic torsion balance as described in a previous communication (Majumdar and Majumdar, *loc. cit.*). The density of the glass sample was then determined by noting the loss in weight in a hydrostatic balance, suspended in a liquid of known specific gravity (nitrobenzene, sp. gr. = 1.1999).

FIG. 1

Gold titration curve with FeSO_4 (no borax).

FIG. 2

Gold titration curve with FeSO_4 (in presence of 200 times borax).

A standard solution of gold was prepared by dissolving 0.5152 g. of purest sample of gold available in aqua regia, evaporating the solution on a water-bath and making the solution up to 250 c.c. A more dilute solution was prepared by diluting 25 c.c. of this solution to 250 c.c. (1 c.c. $\equiv$ 0.0002576 g. of gold). The Mohr salt solution contained 0.01102 g. equiv. per litre. Thus 1 c.c. of the soln. $\equiv$ 0.0007243 g. of Au.

The potentials were measured in a Tinsley potentiometer (Vernier type) against a saturated calomel electrode at room temperature and represented graphically in Figs. 1 and 2.

The following table gives the results of titration with standard gold solutions with and without borax (curves 1, 2, 3).

TABLE I

Titration with standard gold solution.

Au taken (mg.)	... 2.576 (without borax)	0.6645 (without borax)	0.8316 (with borax)
„ found „	... 2.568 (Fig. 1)	0.6539 (Fig. 2)	0.8302 (Fig. 3)

The following table gives the results of gold estimation with different samples of borax glass.

TABLE II

Amount of glass dissolved in 50 c.c. (g.)	... 0.4162	0.3898	0.2769	0.2859	0.2287	0.3004	0.4769
% Au in the sample	... 0.294	1.04	1.284	1.53	1.873	2.23	3.01

Table III gives the values of susceptibility determination of the different samples; density of the different samples of borax glass in nitrobenzene (found, in air at 35°, 1.1999) is shown in column 5. The variation in the specific gravity of glass of the same composition, as is well known, is due to different rates of annealing. This has no effect on the value of the mass susceptibility as will be seen in the following table.

TABLE III

Immersion liquids employed: pyridine ($\kappa_1 = -0.612 \times 10^{-6}$) and diethylaniline ($\kappa_2 = -0.780 \times 10^{-6}$). Density of nitrobenzene found (temp. of air = 35°) = 1.1999.

% Au	θ_1 .	θ_2 .	Vol. sus. κ_0 from $\frac{\theta_1}{\theta_2} = \frac{\kappa_0 - \kappa_1}{\kappa_0 - \kappa_2} \times 10^6$	Sp. gr.	$\chi \times 10^6$
0 (Sample I)	83°.3	63°.3	-1.264	2.334	-0.5418
0 („ II)	100°.0	75°.0	-1.284	2.371	-0.5414
0 („ III)	87°.8	65°.4	-1.2706	2.346	-0.5416
0.294	130°.1	100°.4	-1.348	2.4939	-0.5404
1.040	78°.3	55°.5	-1.189	2.2122	-0.5375
1.284	84°.5	60°.6	-1.206	2.2478	-0.5365
1.530	106°.6	80°.4	-1.295	2.4180	-0.5356
1.873	116°.9	85°.9	-1.246	2.3322	-0.5342
2.230	112°.45	85°.8	-1.321	2.4793	-0.5329
3.010	58°.1	43°.1	-1.2635	2.3823	-0.5298

It will be seen from the above table that there is a gradual decrease of the mass susceptibility of the glass with increasing concentration of gold. This observation is in keeping with the results of similar systems in which polar salts are dispersed, with the difference that the decrease is less in the case under examination.

DISCUSSION

From the observed values of χ for the glass, the mass susceptibility of dissolved gold χ_1 may be calculated from the additivity formula :

$$100\chi = p \cdot \chi_1 + (100 - p) \cdot \chi_2,$$

where χ is the observed mass susceptibility of the glass, χ_1 , that of the dissolved gold, p , its percentage in the glass and χ_2 is the susceptibility of borax glass, which is taken as -0.5417×10^{-6} .

The following table shows the values of χ_1 and atomic susceptibility χ_a of the dissolved gold dispersed in borax glass.

TABLE IV

Conc. of Au.	$\chi_1 \times 10^6$ (calc.).	$\chi_a \times 10^6$ (calc.).	Conc. of Au.	$\chi_1 \times 10^6$ (calc.).	$\chi_a \times 10^6$ (calc.).
0.303%	-0.1512	-29.82	1.912%	-0.1574	-31.03
1.059	-0.1528	-30.13	2.280	-0.1604	-31.63
1.306	-0.1538	-30.33	3.150	-0.1682	-33.16
1.561	-0.1552	-30.61			

χ for pure Au = -0.1500×10^{-6} and $\chi_a = -29.58 \times 10^{-6}$.

The results are represented graphically in Fig. 3.

FIG. 3

Change in susceptibility of Au dissolved in borax.

Although in the case under examination, the increase of diamagnetic susceptibility is not so great as in the case of such systems as $\text{Na}_2\text{SO}_4 - \text{Na}_2\text{B}_4\text{O}_7$ glass, yet the observed increase (about 12% for a gold content of 3.1%) is real and cannot be accounted for by

experimental error. The X-ray diffraction results do not reveal any marked change in the spacing of dissolved gold (Majumdar and Banerjee, *Nature*, 1946, 188, 753).

The glass samples examined by us gave sharp diffraction lines in Debye-Scherer photographs as opposed from diffuse bands obtained with Zsigmondy's gold sols, proving that the process of subdivision of gold in the glass does not proceed to the same fine states as in the colloidal solution (10^{-7} cm). In some cases, slight increase in diamagnetism has also been noticed with subdivision. Thus Rao (*Proc. Ind. Acad. Sci.*, 1935, 2A, 249) has found somewhat larger diamagnetism for colloidal copper than in massive metal. In any case, the relation of magnetic properties of elements with their state of subdivision has not been clearly elucidated.

It should be stated here that the free electrons in the metallic bond might contribute to increased diamagnetism. The so-called Raman-Ehrenfest binding may be present in the glass solution: in this type of binding it is assumed that the valency electrons have large orbits encircling a relatively large number of atoms. Hence, the observed increase in the diamagnetism of gold, dispersed in borax glass, may be due to the expansion of the orbits of the electrons of the metallic bond. But it is doubtful whether the total increase can be explained in this manner.

Whether presence of a dielectric medium can alter the dimensions of a metallic lattice also requires considerations. Unfortunately, the energetics of metallic lattice has not been studied in the same manner as in the case of purely polar lattices. But it may be inferred qualitatively (in analogy to the case of a polar lattice) that a dielectric medium will tend to decrease the binding forces between the constituents of the lattice. As the dielectric constant of borax glass is about 7.5, it may be expected that the gold lattice will be somewhat enlarged when it is formed by the solidification of a melt of borax.

The slope of the curve ($\chi - c$) also presents some difficulties. The extrapolated value of χ for 100% Au does not evidently give the value for pure metal. It is not safe, however, to extrapolate a curve with a maximum concentration of a little over 3% for 100%. The nature of the curve might vary (although this is a purely theoretical possibility, as higher concentrations are not obtained without separation of gold) at higher concentrations of the metal, passing through a maximum point. The whole subject therefore requires clarification and further experiments on similar systems are in progress.

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